

FAIRsFAIR
Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

F-UJI – A FAIR data assessment tool

Robert Huber
rhuber@uni-bremen.de

ExPaNDS Symposium for Librarians and data managers

Project background: FAIR Data Assessment Pilots

- FAIR assessment implementation comprises the development of two main components – **assessment metrics** and **tool**.

Priority Recommendations

Rec. 8: Facilitate automated processing

Rec. 12: Develop metrics for FAIR Digital Objects

Supporting Recommendations

Rec. 25: Implement FAIR metrics to monitor uptake

European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data. 2018. 'Turning FAIR into Reality: Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data.' <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

Assessment Scenarios

For more information, see D4.1 Draft Recommendations on Requirements for Fair Datasets in Certified Repositories, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3678715>

Research data lifecycle; figure adapted from (Mosconi et al., 2019) and scenarios of FAIR assessment of datasets therein.

¹While FAIR principles may apply to any digital objects, we are concerned with the subset of digital objects: research data that are collected, measured, or created for purposes of scientific analysis.

- ✓ FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier
- ✓ FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier
- ✓ FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability
- ✓ FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes
- ✓ FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines
- ✓ FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data
- ✓ FsF-A2-01M - Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available
- ✓ FsF-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language
- ✓ FsF-I1-02M - Metadata uses semantic resources
- ✓ FsF-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
- ✓ FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data
- ✓ FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused
- ✓ FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation
- ✓ FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data
- ✓ FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community

Please [login & comment below](#) citing in the subject line the Metric Identifier No. you are referring to - e.g. "FsF-R1.3-01M"

Object Assessment Metrics v0.4

We would love to hear your feedback!

<https://fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>

From Principles to Practical Tests

Huber, Robert, Cepinskas, Linas, Davidson, Joy, Herterich, Patricia, L'Hours, Hervé, Mokrane, Mustapha, von Stein, Ilona, & Verburg, Maaïke. (2021). D4.5 Report on FAIR Data Assessment Toolset and Badging Scheme (V1.0_DRAFT). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336159>

<https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>

<https://www.f-uji.net>

F-UJI – An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool

The screenshot displays the F-UJI API interface. At the top, the URL `/fuji/api/v1/openapi.json` is entered in the search bar, with an **Explore** button. Below this, the **F-UJI 1.0.0 OAS3** title is shown, along with a link to the OpenAPI specification and a description: "A Service for Evaluating Research Data Objects Based on FAIRsFAIR Metrics." A note mentions support from the FAIRsFAIR project (H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 Grant Agreement 831558). Links for "Contact the developer", "MIT License", and "Find out more about F-UJI" are provided.

The **Servers** section shows `/fuji/api/v1` selected. A red arrow points from the **Authorize** button to the **Code** tab of the response details. The **Code** tab shows a **200** status and the following **Response body** (JSON):

```
{
  "metric_identifier": "FsF-F1-02D",
  "metric_name": "Persistent identifier",
  "output": {
    "pid": "https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902845",
    "pid_scheme": "doi",
    "resolvable_status": true,
    "resolved_url": "https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.902845"
  },
  "passed": true,
  "score": {
    "earned": 1,
    "total": 1
  },
  "test_debug": [
    "INFO: Persistence identifier scheme - doi",
    "INFO: Retrieving page http://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902845",
    "INFO: Request status code - 200",
    "INFO: Found HTML page"
  ]
},
{
  "id": 3,
  "metric_identifier": "FsF-F2-01M",
  "metric_name": "Descriptive (core) metadata",
  "output": {
    "core_metadata_found": {
      "creator": [
        "Bärfuss, Konrad",

```

The **Response headers** section shows:

```
content-length: 5116
content-type: application/json
date: Fri, 24 Apr 2020 17:14:06 GMT
server: Werkzeug/1.0.0 Python/3.7.6
```

The interface also shows a **FAIR object** section with a **POST /evaluate** endpoint and a **FAIR metric** section with a **GET /metrics** endpoint. A **Download** button is visible in the response details panel.

High Level Flow (Data Gathering)

Metadata collation

- **Domain agnostic standards:** Dublin Core, schema.org/Dataset, DataCite, and DCAT-2 (XML, RDF, or JSON) , MODS (METS) (XML)
- **Microdata:** OpenGraph, RDFa
- **Feeds:** OAI-ORE, atom or GeoRSS
- **Structured data:** RDF, RDFa, JSON-LD, turtle etc
- **Domain specific:** DDI Codebook, ISO 19115 (ISO 19139) EML

F-UJI – An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool

Assessment Results:

Evaluated Resource:

Data for: Bar chart of ceramic building material quantities by context type and Bar chart of ceramic building material MSW by context type and Ceramic building materials by context type (excluding Phase 6).

Save JSON New

FAIR level: initial

Resource PID/URL: <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.14473>

DataCite support: enabled

Metric Version: metrics_v0.4

Metric Specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

Software version: v1.3.8

Download assessment results: [\(JSON\)](#)

Save and share assessment results:

Saved assessments:

- 2021-09-17 initial
- 2021-09-20 initial
- 2021-09-21 initial
- 2021-09-21 initial

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	5 of 7	moderate
Accessible:	1.5 of 3	initial
Interoperable:	1 of 4	initial
Reusable:	3 of 10	initial

<https://www.f-uji.net>

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✓

FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✓

FAIR level: 3 of 3 advanced

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "pid": "http://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.14473",
  "pid_scheme": "doi",
  "resolvable_status": true,
  "resolved_url": "https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/268269"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-F1-02D-1	Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0.5	1	✓
FsF-F1-02D-2	Persistent identifier is resolvable	0.5	3	✓

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	PID schemes-based assessment supported by the assessment service - [ark, 'arxiv', 'bioproject', 'biosample', 'doi', 'ensembl', 'genome', 'gnd', 'handle', 'lsid', 'pmid', 'pmcid', 'purl', 'refseq', 'sra', 'uniprot', 'urn']
INFO	Retrieving page -: http://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.14473 as text/html, application/xhtml+xml, application/xml;q=0.5, text/xml;q=0.5, application/rdf+xml;q=0.5
INFO	Content negotiation accept=text/html, application/xhtml+xml, application/xml;q=0.5, text/xml;q=0.5, application/rdf+xml;q=0.5, status=200
INFO	Found HTML page!
INFO	Object identifier active (status code = 200)
SUCCESS	Persistence identifier scheme -: doi

FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✓

FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ?

FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically. ✓

Testing & Consultation – the pilots

Repository	Certification	Subject Areas	Datasets Evaluated (as of 25.09.2020)	FAIR Data Improvement	Repository Contact
PANGAEA	CoreTrustSeal, WDS Regular Member				
Phaidra-Italy	CoreTrustSeal				
CSIRO Data Portal	CoreTrustSeal				
World Data Centre for Climate (WDCC)	CoreTrustSeal, WDS Regular Member				
DataverseNO	CoreTrustSeal				

FAIRSFAR Object Metric	Comment	Next Step
FsF-F1-01D Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	OK	
FsF-F1-02D Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	OK	
FsF-F2-01M Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	Some datasets do not have a summary/abstract. e.g., https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.863175	Uwe: Most child datasets don't have abstract, but their parents. Abstract is optional field (datacite schema) For new datasets, abstract is recommended especially for datasets with publications. Routine (automatic from sensor) dataset don't have abstract
FsF-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	OK	
FsF-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	OK	
FsF-A1-01M Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	Total score = 1, Earned = 0 NO access information is available in metadata: Possible ways to include access level metadata are: Schema.org <ul style="list-style-type: none"> if public use => isAccessibleForFree free (Note: isAccessibleForFree Supersedes free)	Action: Uwe to include access level in the metadata (Done) <input type="checkbox"/>

Before and After

FAIR Scores of PANGAEA Datasets By Principle (Before Improvement, n=500)

FAIR Scores of PANGAEA Datasets By Principle (After Improvement, n=500)

Lessons learned

- Automatised FAIR assessment of research data objects is possible
- Supporting a very large and diverse community
 - 5 pilots
 - + CESSDA, EOSC-NORDIC, DataverseNL
- Iterative mutual improvements ... ongoing process

Best use formula: (F-UJI FAIR assessment + f2f FAIR consulting)

Thank You

Task 4.5:

Anusuriya Devaraju, Robert Huber,
Mustapha Mokrane, Jerry de Vries,
Patricia Herterich, Linas Cepinkas, Vesa
Akerman, Joy Davidson, Herve L'Hours.

FAIR-Aware

Let's assume you have research data almost ready for uploading to a repository: do you already know how you and the repository can work together to make the data as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) as possible? By guiding you through the assessment process, the FAIR-Aware tool can help you to better understand the FAIR Principles and how making data FAIR can increase the potential value and impact of your data.

FAIR-Aware is an online tool developed by the FAIRSFAR project. The tool is not meant to give you a score for the FAIRness of a specific dataset. You should, however, have a target dataset in mind to be able to answer the questions and complete the assessment.

The assessment starts with a few questions 'about you' followed by 10 questions about FAIR. After you answer each question additional information and guidance will be displayed. The majority of the questions will help you assess your current level of awareness about what actions are needed to make data FAIR. At the end, Your feedback will help us improve FAIR-Aware and make it as user-friendly as possible. You will need between 10 and 30 minutes to complete the assessment depending on your familiarity with the subject and issues covered.

The FAIRSFAR Team (DANS, DCC, UniHB)

Find out more about FAIRSFAR on the project's website. If you have any questions, drop us an e-mail.

About you

Which research domain do you work in? Domain

Which of the following describes your role? Please select all that apply.

- | | |
|--|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher | <input type="checkbox"/> Funder |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Policy maker | <input type="checkbox"/> Publisher |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research support (e.g. data steward, curator, data manager, librarian, information technology professional) | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

Which of the following types of organisations best describe your employer? Please select all that apply.

- | | |
|--|---------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research Infrastructure/eInfrastructure (e.g. data repository, service provider, library) | <input type="checkbox"/> Funding Body |
| <input type="checkbox"/> University or Research Performing Organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Publisher |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research Performing Organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Industry |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Government | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> eInfrastructure (e.g. repository or scientific data provider) | |

FAIR questions

FINDABLE

Are you aware that a dataset should be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier when deposited with a data repository? Yes No

Are you aware that when you deposit a dataset with a repository, you will need to provide some details (known as discovery metadata) in order to make the data findable, understandable and reusable to others? Yes No